

III WORKSHOP

IMPLICAÇÃO DE MODIFICAÇÕES METABÓLICAS E EPIGENÉTICAS PARA A NEUROPROTEÇÃO: RELEVÂNCIA PARA A PESQUISA TRANSLACIONAL

Faculdade De Ciências Médicas da Santa Casa de São Paulo
São Paulo/SP, Brasil

11, 12 e 13 de Junho de 2018

APOIO:

FACULDADE DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS DA SANTA CASA DE SÃO PAULO
DEPARTAMENTO DE CIÊNCIAS FISIOLÓGICAS

III WORKSHOP:

***Implicação de modificações metabólicas e epigenéticas para a neuroproteção:
relevância para a pesquisa translacional***

***Implication of metabolic and epigenetic modifications for neuroprotection:
relevance to translational research.***

Responsável: Profa. Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock

São Paulo, Junho 2018

1. INFORMAÇÕES GERAIS

1.1.A. RESUMO

No workshop apresentado aqui daremos enfoque a uma abordagem integrada dos principais mecanismos que podem interferir com o funcionamento neural e, por consequência, levar a morte celular. Dentre os processos, destacaremos modificações metabólicas e epigenéticas, onde a mitocôndria possui um papel chave.

Além disso, destacaremos ao longo do III Workshop diversas doenças neurodegenerativas e neuropsiquiátricas como Doença de Huntington, Doença de Alzheimer, Doença de Parkinson, Esclerose Lateral Amiotrófica, Esquizofrenia e Autismo, uma vez que são consideradas como as implicações finais da desregulação e/ou morte celular. Abordaremos também possíveis estratégias terapêuticas que possam, num futuro próximo, permitir a reversão da disfunção neural e consequentemente as suas manifestações clínicas.

1.1.B. ABSTRACT

In the workshop presented herein it will be addressed an integrated approach of the main mechanisms related to neural function and, consequently, that can lead to cell death. Among the processes, we will focus on metabolic and epigenetic alterations, where mitochondrial plays a major role.

Additionally, we will highlight along the III Workshop several neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric disorders such as Huntington's disease, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, Schizophrenia and Autism, once they are considered as final consequences of cellular deregulation and/or death. Therapeutic strategies that can be, in a close future, counteract neural deregulation and consequently clinical manifestations will be debated too.

1.2.A. OBJETIVO

O principal objetivo do workshop é fornecer a base do conhecimento de como alterações na transcrição gênica, incluindo modificações epigenéticas, podem interferir com o metabolismo celular, onde as mitocôndrias são o foco principal, e vice-versa, e como tal desregulação pode levar ao mau funcionamento neural e por fim a sua morte. Pretendemos ainda, como mencionado anteriormente, discutir mecanismos que possam levar a neuroproteção devido a interferência em diferentes vias de sinalização celular - todos os tópicos do workshop estão descritos na **seção 2**. Consequentemente, esperamos ainda mostrar a importância da ciência básica na pesquisa translacional e a sua contextualização no mundo atual.

1.2.B. GOAL

The goal of this workshop is to provide knowledge of how transcription deregulation, including epigenetic modification, can interfere with cellular metabolism, where mitochondrial is the main

focus, and *vice-versa*, and how this deregulation can lead to neural dysfunction and, finally, cell death. We also aim, as already mentioned, to discuss mechanisms that can lead to neuroprotection due to the interference in different signaling pathways – all the topics are described in **section 2**. Consequently, we expect to show the importance of basic science in translational research and its current contextualization.

2. TÓPICOS DO WORKSHOP

- Bases moleculares da epigenética;
- Moduladores de lisinas deacetilases (HDACs clássicas e sirtuínas)
- Mitocôndrias e o metabolismo celular;
- Modificações epigenéticas e metabólicas e sua co-relação com a morte neural;
- Alterações metabólicas e/ou epigenéticas em doenças neurodegenerativas;
- Alterações metabólicas e/ou epigenéticas em doenças neuropsiquiátricas;
- Neurodegeneração *versus* neuroproteção

3. ÁREAS CORRELATAS

1. Metabolismo e Bioenergética
2. Biologia Celular e Molecular
3. Epigenética
4. Neurociências

4. INSITUIÇÕES ENVOLVIDAS

Faculdade de Ciências Médicas da Santa Casa de São Paulo (FCMSCSP)

Universidade Federal de São Paulo (UNIFESP), Campus São Paulo

5.A. MEMBROS DA COMISSÃO ORGANIZADORA

Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock (Profa. Assistente, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – COORDENADORA E MEMBRO DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA

Hudson Buck (Prof. Titular e Chefe do Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – MEMBRO DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA E CO-RESPONSÁVEL PELA ORGANIZAÇÃO DO EVENTO

Isaías Glezer (Prof. Adjunto, Dept. Bioquímica, UNIFESP) – MEMBRO DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA

Luciana Malavolta Quaglio (Profa. Adjunto, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – MEMBRO DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA

Tânia Araújo Viel (Prof. Doutor 2, Escola de Artes, Ciências e Humanidades da Universidade de São Paulo, USP) – MEMBRO DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA

5.B. ORGANIZING COMMITTEE MEMBERS

Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock (Profa. Assistente, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – ORGANIZER, SCIENTIFIC COMMISSION MEMBER (ABSTRACTS AND CURRICULUM EVALUATOR) AND RESPONSIBLE FOR THE WORKSHOP ORGANIZATION

Hudson Buck (Prof. Titular e Chefe do Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – SCIENTIFIC COMMISSION MEMBER (ABSTRACTS AND CURRICULUM EVALUATOR) AND RESPONSIBLE FOR THE WORKSHOP ORGANIZATION

Isaías Glezer (Prof. Adjunto, Dept. Bioquímica, UNIFESP) – SCIENTIFIC COMMISSION MEMBER (ABSTRACTS AND CURRICULUM EVALUATOR)

Luciana Malavolta Quaglio (Profa. Adjunto, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP) – SCIENTIFIC COMMISSION MEMBER (ABSTRACTS AND CURRICULUM EVALUATOR)

Tânia Araújo Viel (Prof. Doutor 2, Escola de Artes, Ciências e Humanidades da Universidade de São Paulo, USP) – SCIENTIFIC COMMISSION MEMBER (ABSTRACTS AND CURRICULUM EVALUATOR)

6. DOCENTES PARTICIPANTES DA COMISSÃO CIENTÍFICA

Hudson Buck (Prof. Titular e Chefe do Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP);

Isaías Glezer (Prof. Adjunto, Dept. Bioquímica, UNIFESP);

Luciana Malavolta Quaglio (Profa. Adjunto, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP);

Tânia Araújo Viel (Prof. Doutor 2, Escola de Artes, Ciências e Humanidades, USP)

Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock (Profa. Assistente, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP);

7. DOCENTES PARTICIPANTES DO WORKSHOP (ORDEM ALFABÉTICA)

Ana Paula de Melo Loureiro (Faculdade de Ciências Farmacêuticas, Departamento de Análises Clínicas e Toxicológicas, USP, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1861501477882217>

Ana Paula Morales (Co-fundadora da Data14 e Editora Executiva da revista Ciência e Cultura); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/8574340461702232>

Anibal Eugenio Vercesi (Prof. Titular e Livre Docente do Dept. Bioquímica da UNICAMP, Campinas, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/9773431959774087>

Ary Gadelha de Alencar Araripe Neto (Prof. Adjunto, Departamento de Bioquímica, Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP/Campus Vila Clementino, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/8107200180236710>

Denise Carleto Andia (Health Science Institute, Dental Research Division, UNIP, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/6206973806137260>

Diogo Ventura Lovato (Researcher at Timoo); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/3610599627040169>

Fernanda Marques da Cunha (Profa. Adjunto, Departamento de Bioquímica, Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP/Campus Vila Clementino, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/4457893486819547>

Gabriel Andrade Alves (Repórter de Ciência e Saúde - Jornal Folha de S.Paulo, Editor interino de Ciência e Saúde - Jornal Folha de S.Paulo e Responsável pelo blog Cadê a Cura? (folha.com/cadeacura), da Folha de S.Paulo); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/9619712171770037>

Isaías Glezer (Prof. Adjunto, Dept. Bioquímica, Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP/Campus Vila Clementino, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/6158025931975591>

Joana Gil-Mohapel (Profa. Adjunto, Island Medical Program, UBC Faculty of Medicine, University of Victoria e MEDD421 & MEDD422 Course Co-Director, Victoria, Canadá); https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joana_Gil-Mohapel

Marcelo Mori (Prof. Doutor Dept. Bioquímica e Biologia Tecidual, Instituto de Biologia, UNICAMP); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/3425809117024031>

Maria Luiza Silveira Mello (Profa. Titular Livre-Docente Dept. Genética, UNICAMP); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/4241804239085387>

Miriam Galvonas Jasiulionis (Professora Associada e Chefe do Laboratório Ontogenética e Epigenética, Dept. de Farmacologia da Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP/Campus Vila Clementino, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/3057188718614807>

Patrícia de Souza Brocardo (Profa. Dept. de Ciências Morfológicas, UFSC); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1937185573154113>

Regina Pekelmann Markus (Professora Titular, Laboratório de Cronofarmacologia, Instituto de Biociências, USP, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1924851134659071>

Rubens Harb Bollos (MD, PhD, Laboratório Ontogenética e Epigenética Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP/Campus Vila Clementino, São Paulo, Brasil); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/4068748252174323>

Sovan Sarkar (Birmingham Fellow, Lecturer/Assistant Professor, Independent Group Leader, Institute of Cancer and Genomic Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK); https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Sovan_Sarkar;
<http://www.birmingham.ac.uk/staff/profiles/cancer-genomic/sarkar-sovan.aspx>

Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock (Profa. Assistente, Dept. Ciências Fisiológicas, FCMSCSP); <http://lattes.cnpq.br/8336590636180811>

Tiago Fleming Outeiro (Department of Experimental Neurodegeneration, Center for Nanoscale Microscopy and Molecular Physiology of the Brain, University Medical Center Goettingen, Germany); https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Tiago_Outeiro

- - - - -

8.1. CRONOGRAMA 1 – PANORAMA GERAL

Duração: 3 dias	11/06/2018 (2ªFEIRA) 12/06/2018 (3ªFEIRA) 13/06/2018 (4ªFEIRA)
Cronograma:	8:30 às 10:30 – Apresentações 10:30 às 11:00 - Coffee break 11:00 às 13:00 – Apresentações 14:00 às 15:20 – Apresentações 15:30 às 16:00 - Coffee break 16:00 às 17:30 – Apresentações

8.2. CRONOGRAMA 2 – PROGRAMA PRELIMINAR

Dia 1 – 11/06/2018 (2ªFEIRA)

8:30 – INICIO DO EVENTO INSCRIÇÕES E ENTREGA DE MATERIAL

9:00 às 09:40 – SESSÃO DE ABERTURA

The role of structural plasticity in Huntington's Disease – Profa. Joana Gil (Uvic, Canadá);

09:50 às 10:30 – MESA REDONDA

Dual effect of local melatonin synthesized and exogenous melatonin in the selective protection of the cerebellum against intracerebroventricular (icv) LPS – Profa. Regina Markus (USP);

10:30 às 11:00 – COFFEE BREAK

MÓDULO 1: MODIFICAÇÕES EPIGENÉTICA

11:00 às 13:00 – APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Profa. Fernanda Marques da Cunha (UNIFESP); Aluno 1

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): A definir.

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Valproic acid effects on chromatin epigenetic marks - Profa. Maria Luiza Silveira Mello (UNICAMP);

Apresentação 3 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Redefining Neurodegenerative Diseases through Epigenetics - Prof. Tiago Outeiro (UGoettingem, Alemanha);

13:00 às 14:00 – ALMOÇO

MÓDULO 2: PAPEL MITOCONDRIAL EM PROCESSOS FISIOLÓGICOS E PATOLÓGICOS

14:00 às 15:20 – APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Profa. Maria Luiza Silveira Mello (UNICAMP); Aluno 2

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Investigating the role of the Δ TG mutation in *XPC* gene on expression of the transcriptional co-activator PGC-1 α - Mateus Prates Mori (USP);

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Mitochondrial effects of life span-extending interventions in *Caenorhabditis elegans* - Profa. Fernanda Marques da Cunha (UNIFESP);

15:30 às 16:00 – COFFEE BREAK

16:00 às 17:00 – SESSÃO DE PÔSTER – Avaliação

17:00 às 17:30 – Closing remarks (followed by networking opportunities and discussion)

Dia 2 – 12/06/2018 (3ªFEIRA)

MÓDULO 3: ALTERAÇÕES METABÓLICAS E/OU EPIGENÉTICAS E SUA RELAÇÃO COM O DESENVOLVIMENTO DE DOENÇAS – Parte I

8:30 às 10:30 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Prof. Tatiana Rosenstock (FCMSCSP); Aluno 3

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): SIRT1 regulates *Mxd1* throughout melanoma progression - Profa. Mirian Jasiulionis (UNIFESP);

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Epigenetic biomarkers and resilience as a key to predict relapse in drug addictions treatment - Dr. Rubens H. Bollos (UNIFESP);

Apresentação 3 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Cellular alterations in the course of benzo[a]pyrene induced transformation and implications for chemoprevention - Profa. Ana Paula de Melo Loureiro (USP);

10:30 às 11:00 – COFFEE BREAK

11:00 às 13:00 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Profa. Marcelo Mori (UNICAMP); Aluno 4

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Epigenetic regulation in mesenchymal stem cells - Profa. Denise Carleto Andia (UNIP)

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Delaying Aging and Improving Metabolism with Drugs that Target miRNA Biogenesis - Prof. Marcelo Mori (UNICAMP);

Apresentação 3 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Unravelling the Role of Posttranslational Modifications on Alpha-Synuclein Biology and Pathobiology - Prof. Tiago Outeiro (UGoettingem, Alemanha);

13:00 às 14:00 – ALMOÇO

MÓDULO 4: ALTERAÇÕES METABÓLICAS E/OU EPIGENÉTICAS E SUA RELAÇÃO COM O DESENVOLVIMENTO DE DOENÇAS – Parte II

14:00 às 15:20 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Profa. Mirian Jasiulionis (UNIFESP); Aluno 5

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Mitochondrial bioenergetics and redox state in metabolic diseases – Prof. Anibal Vercesi (UNICAMP);

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): In vitro screening platforms in mammalian cells to identify autophagy modulators for therapeutic interventions in neurodegenerative disorders - Prof. Sovan Sarkar (Univ. Birmingham, UK);

15:30 às 16:00 – COFFEE BREAK

16:00 às 17:00 – SESSÃO DE PÔSTER – Avaliação

17:00 às 17:30 – Closing remarks (followed by networking opportunities and discussion)

Dia 3- 13/06/2018 (4ª FEIRA)

MÓDULO 5: NEURODEGENERAÇÃO VERSUS NEUROPROTEÇÃO

8:30 às 10:30 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Prof. Isaías Glezer (UNIFESP); Aluno 6

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Neuroprotection by modulation of hippocampal neurogenesis: potential therapeutic effects in models of depression and stress - Profa. Joana Gil (UVic, Canadá);

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Antidepressant effects of probucol in early-symptomatic YAC128 Huntington's disease transgenic mice - Profa. Patrícia de Souza Brocardo (UFSC);

Apresentação 3 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Targeting autophagy dysfunction in rare childhood neurodegenerative diseases as a common pathway for therapeutic interventions - Prof. Sovan Sarkar (Univ. Birmingham, UK);

10:30 às 11:00 – COFFEE BREAK

11:00 às 13:00 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Profa. Patrícia Brocardo (UFSC); Aluno 7

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): The role of genetics and epigenetics in Autism Spectrum Disorder - Dr. Diogo Ventura Lovato (Tismoo, The Biotech Company)

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Mitochondrial dysfunction as a consequence of hypoxia and their role to the development of Schizophrenia - Profa. Tatiana Rosenstock (FCMSCSP);

Apresentação 3 (35 min; 05 min discussão): Effects of excitotoxic neuronal cell death on hypothalamic neurogenesis and neural precursor cells (NPCs) mitochondrial respiration - Prof. Isaías Glezer (UNIFESP);

13:00 às 14:00 – ALMOÇO

MÓDULO 6: BUSCA DE NOVAS ALTERNATIVAS DIAGNÓSTICAS E TERAPÊUTICAS E IMPORTÂNCIA DA PESQUISA TRANSLACIONAL

14:00 às 15:20 - APRESENTAÇÕES

Chair: Prof. Hudson Buck (FCMSCSP); Aluno 8

Apresentação 1 (35 min; 05 min discussão): A definir.

Apresentação 2 (35 min; 05 min discussão): New diagnostic approaches in mental disorders - Prof. Ary Gadelha (UNIFESP);

15:30 às 16:00 – COFFEE BREAK

16:00 às 17:00 – ENCERRAMENTO

Vamos falar de Ciência? Como transmitir informações científicas na era da pós verdade.

Como a sociedade percebe e interage com a Ciência - Ana Paula Morales (Data14);

Como informar na era em que fatos não bastam? - Gabriel Alves (Folha de São Paulo)

09. CONTATOS

Ana Paula de Melo Loureiro <apmlou@usp.br>

Ana Paula Morales <ana.morales@data14.com.br>

Anibal Eugenio Vercesi <anibal@unicamp.br>

Ary Gadelha <aryararipe@gmail.com>

Denise Andia <denise.andia@docente.unip.br>

Diogo Ventura Lovato <diogo@tismoo.com.br>

Fernanda Marques da Cunha <phernandacunha@gmail.com>

Gabriel Alves <gabriel.alves@grupofolha.com.br>

Isaias Glezer <iglezer@unifesp.br>

Joana Gil-Mohapel <igil@uvic.ca>

Marcelo Mori <marcelo.mori@unifesp.br>

Maria Luisa Mello <mlsmello@unicamp.br>

Mateus Prates Mori <mori_mateus@yahoo.com.br>

Miriam Jasiulionis <mjasiulionis@gmail.com>

Patrícia Brocardo <patibrocardo@gmail.com>

Regina Pekelmann Markus <rpmarkus@usp.br>

Rubens Bollos <rubensbollos@teofilo.com.br>

Sovan Sarkar <s.sarkar@bham.ac.uk>

Tatiana Rosado <tatiana.rosado@fcmsantacasasp.edu.br>

Tiago Fleming Outeiro <touteiro@gmail.com>

10. FONTES DE FINANCIAMENTO TRABALHOS A SEREM APRESENTADOS

COORDENAÇÃO DE APERFEIÇOAMENTO DE PESSOAL DE NÍVEL SUPERIOR (CAPES)
CONSELHO NACIONAL DE DESENVOLVIMENTO CIENTÍFICO E TECNOLÓGICO (CNPQ)
FACULDADE DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS DA SANTA CASA DE SÃO PAULO (FCMSCSP)
FUNDO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA DA FCMSCSP (FAP)
FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO (FAPESP)

11. FONTES DE PATROCÍNIO MATERIAL E COFFEE BREAK

Resumos Apresentações Docentes

Presentation:

Title:

Cellular alterations in the course of benzo[a]pyrene induced transformation and implications for chemoprevention.

Tiago Franco de Oliveira¹, Everson Willian Fialho Cordeiro¹, Matheus Relvas dos Santos¹, Joseana de Oliveira¹, Giovanna Caroline Silva¹, Marisa Helena Gennari de Medeiros², Paolo Di Mascio², Ana Paula de Melo Loureiro¹ - ¹Departamento de Análises Clínicas e Toxicológicas, Faculdade de Ciências Farmacêuticas, Universidade de São Paulo, SP; ²Departamento de Bioquímica, Instituto de Química, Universidade de São Paulo, SP.

Abstract:

Normal human bronchial epithelial cells (BEAS-2B) exposed to the carcinogen benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P) for 7 days acquire the transformed phenotype, as assessed in the group by their anchorage independent colony growth in soft agar. This cell transformation model was partially characterized by performing targeted metabolomics focused on intermediates of glycolysis, citric acid cycle, some amino acids, and nucleotides, whose profiles, in comparison to control cells, changed along the period of exposure. Altered DNA methylation, cell cycle, glucose uptake, levels of excreted DNA lesions, and succinate dehydrogenase activity followed the metabolic changes. Since the levels of the analyzed intermediates were changed as early as 1 h after B[a]P exposure, a detailed knowledge of the altered metabolic pathways will shed light on possible targets for interventions to prevent the affected cells to follow their ways towards transformation. In an initial approach concerning this goal, we tested the effect of nicotinamide riboside (NR, 1 μ M) supplementation (to increase the intracellular NAD⁺ levels that were decreased soon after the addition of B[a]P) concomitantly to B[a]P (1 μ M) along 7 days. We found a protective effect of NR against cell transformation, without changing the viability of the normal cells. The systematic investigation of the profiles of intermediate metabolites and metabolic fluxes in this model will highlight key changes that may be associated with the shift from the transformed to the non-transformed phenotype, opening new possibilities to test and establish chemopreventive approaches.

Financing: FAPESP, CNPq, CAPES, PRP/USP, CEPID Redoxoma

Presentation:

Title:

Como a sociedade percebe e interage com a ciência?

Ana Paula Morales, Data14.

Abstract:

A população de uma forma geral tem grande interesse por temas de ciência e tecnologia, e a grande mídia é sua principal fonte de informação sobre assuntos da área. Mas, como a sociedade percebe a pesquisa científica, a valoriza e interage com temas de ciência? Estudos de percepção pública da ciência buscam entender essa relação, como uma forma de promover a comunicação e a cultura científica. Nesta palestra serão abordados os principais resultados de pesquisas nessa área no Brasil e no mundo e reflexões sobre as formas de interação entre ciência e sociedade.

Presentation:

Title:

New diagnostic approaches in mental disorders.

Ary Gadelha, UNIFESP.

Abstract:

Mental disorders (MDs) are currently categorized and diagnosed as clinical syndromes. Each syndrome is operationalized in a list of symptoms occurring in specific time ranges. This structure enhanced diagnostic reliability, but lacks construct validity, since it relies solely on clinical observation rather than etiology or pathophysiology. As conceptualized, MDs display clinical heterogeneity since symptoms can be combined in numerous manners in each syndrome. In addition, distinct disorders may present similar characteristics since the same symptoms, e.g. depressed mood, insomnia and attention difficulties, may be present in different syndromes.

Official psychiatric classification systems such as DSM 5 allow comorbidity between disorders. Almost 50% of individuals with a mental disorder have one or more comorbidity, with 22% carrying 2 diagnoses and 23%, 3 or more diagnosis. Even so, throughout the lifespan, MDs demonstrate great overlap with both heterotypic and homotypic continuity described, and comorbidity is rather the rule than the exception.

The overlap between diagnostic criteria and behavioral dimensions weakens the applicability of preventive disease-specific interventions. The scenario is even more complex considering the diagnostic instability during early phases of development particularly during childhood and adolescence. Moreover, high comorbidity rates are likely due to substantial commonalities in underlying biological mechanisms.

Such scenario directed efforts towards new diagnostic approaches, mainly the search for nosological entities based on etiology. Thus, biomarkers and translational research are essential tools to advance the field.

Presentation:

Title:

Epigenetic regulation in mesenchymal stem cells.

Denise Carleto Andia - Pesquisador permanente do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Clínica Odontológica e Faculdade de Odontologia – Instituto de Ciências da Saúde Universidade Paulista – UNIP, São Paulo; Pesquisador colaborador do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Clínica Odontológica Área Concentração em Periodontia - Faculdade de Odontologia de Piracicaba FOP – UNICAMP, Piracicaba.

Equipe: Francesca Racca – IC, FOP/UNICAMP; Natália Cecchi – IC, UNIP; Arthur Georg Schmidt – Doutorando, UNIP; Rahyza I F Assis – Doutoranda, FOP/UNICAMP;

Abstract:

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) can give rise to some tissues and they are promising candidates for tissue repair and regenerative therapies in a broad range of diseases. However, the molecular mechanisms underlying their stemness and differentiation are not well understood. There is still a lack of information available regarding their epigenetic background and regulation. Since cell fate is determined by lineage specific gene regulation and underlying epigenetic mechanisms, such information is mandatory to safely apply MSCs in human clinical trials.

The first part of the talk focus on the epigenetic regulation of MSCs, exploring the possibility of using RG108, an epi-drug and demethylating agent, in MSCs-based cell therapies. Although RG108 was specifically designed to target DNMT enzymes, its effect on the epigenetic machinery itself as well as genome-wide is still unknown. Therefore, the results will explore the ability of RG108 to trigger global changes in DNA methylation and hydroxymethylation levels in addition to gene-specific effects on epigenetic machinery and markers of MSCs multipotency.

The second part of the talk focus on filling the gap of a better understanding of osteogenesis and mesenchymal stem cell differentiation at the molecular level. Comparative results from genome wide changes in DNA methylation and hydroxymethylation of MSCs with distinct osteogenic potential during osteogenic differentiation will be demonstrated to determine their effect on bone-specific gene transcription. The methylation/hydroxymethylation profiles of

MSCs populations with high and low osteogenic potential will be discussed by aiming to select potential epigenetic markers of preferential differentiation towards osteoblasts. While some classic chromosomic regions were highlighted in the genome wide analysis as being related to osteogenic process, some new regions, such as enhancers, were also pointed out. In line with this, novel regulators of osteogenic differentiation have been under investigation.

Specific details of methodologies employed, such as DNA glycosylation before restriction enzymes reaction and DNA oxidation before bisulfite conversion will be provided, aiming to explore the relevance of distinguish between DNA methylation and hydroxymethylation. Since DNA hydroxymethylation roles are not yet well established, this disambiguation is extremely important to accurately detect the different levels between 5mC and 5hmC, and therefore, highlighting their different roles.

Presentation:

Title:

The role of genetics and epigenetics in Autism Spectrum Disorder.

Diogo Ventura Lovato

Research Scientist at Tismoo

Abstract:

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterized by social and communication impairments associated with repetitive and restrict behaviours. Inside the autistic spectrum, there are a huge heterogeneity of etiology, comorbidity and clinical conditions. ASD affects 1 in 67 children with a 4:1 male / female ratio according to the most recent surveys and researches in North American. Despite the alarmism about the worldwide increasing of ASD prevalence, changes in diagnostic criteria associated with increased awareness and education about ASD have been shown to be the most significant factors. Several environmental factors are being studied but scientific evidences showed most of them have very low absolute influence on ASD risk. Since twins and siblings studies on the 70's, scientists and clinicians knew that ASD was a genetic disorder even thought there were different associated genetic alterations and clinical phenotypes. Current knowledge estimates ASD risk is strongly associated to genetics ranging from 70% to 90% including hundreds of different genes. There are ASD patients with mendelian conditions such as Rett Syndrome and Phelan-McDermid Syndrome with single nucleotide variations to chromosomal copy number variations. Generally, these cases are named as "syndromic ASD" and it is a part of clinical features. The majority of ASD cases are named as "idiopathic ASD" and they are caused by multiple genetic alterations, which could be inherited and/or "de novo" mutations, associated with environmental factors. The most important genes associated with ASD are biologically related in molecular pathways related to synaptogenesis, synaptic functions and epigenetic regulators. They are very important to neurodevelopment and could be also clinically associated to other disorders as epilepsy and intellectual disability, for example. One of the main goal in ASD genetics is personalized medicine and segregation of patients to improve clinical trials. There are several emerging research areas in ASD genetics and drug therapies coming from Systems Biology, inheritance polygenic models to drug development and drug repurposing from epigenetic targets.

Presentation:

Title:

Mitochondrial effects of life span-extending interventions in *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

Fernanda Marques da Cunha

Departamento de Bioquímica, Escola Paulista de Medicina, UNIFESP, São Paulo, SP

Abstract:

Life expectancy has been increasing during the last one hundred and fifty years in a way that in two thousand and fifty all the continents will have an increase in the elderly population of at least 30%. Unfortunately the increase in longevity is usually accompanied by an increase in age-related diseases. We know today that decreases in mitochondrial mass and/or function are a hallmark of aging, indicating that those organelles are key players in the aging process. In the effort to understand aging, the worm *C. elegans* has been extensively used, and data show that a number of genetic and non-genetic interventions increase *C. elegans* life span. Curiously, the effects of such life span-extending interventions on mitochondrial activity in worms are unknown. Because mitochondria are crucial for homeostasis maintenance and key players in the aging process, the effects of germline ablation and dietary restriction, two life span-extending interventions, on *C. elegans* mitochondrial activity were investigated. Results show that both interventions reduced oxygen consumption and mitochondrial mass in live worms. Interestingly, mitochondria isolated from animals submitted to life span-extending interventions were more able to oxidize lipids and were also more efficient in using the energy released by lipid oxidation to synthesize ATP. Strikingly, mitochondrial efficiency for the use of lipids as an energy source and life-span were highly correlated suggesting that this is an important parameter for longevity in this animal. Together, the results indicate that low amounts of mitochondria with high capacity and efficiency to oxidize lipids are determinant for the outcomes of life span-extending interventions in *C. elegans*.

Presentation:

Title:

How to report in the era in which facts are not enough?

Gabriel Andrade Alves, Folha de São Paulo

Abstract:

Recently the world has seen an epidemic of fake news and discussions about this matter. What is fake news? How are they born? What motivates someone to create or propagate dubious content? Now the answers are being drafted and the objective of this presentation to shed light on the issue.

Presentation:

Title:

Effects of excitotoxic neuronal cell death on hypothalamic neurogenesis and neural precursor cells (NPCs) mitochondrial respiration.

Isaias Glezer, Departamento de Bioquímica, Escola Paulista de Medicina, Universidade Federal de São Paulo.

Abstract:

Adult neurogenesis can be modulated by microglial activation and neural injury, resulting in different outcomes of regenerative responses. The effects of microglia activation on hypothalamic neurogenesis, a process that impacts brain regions involved in the body energetic balance, is not completely understood. In this study we evaluated whether neuronal lesions in the hypothalamus provoked by monosodium glutamate (MSG) activates a distinct microglial subpopulation associated with the hypothalamic neurogenic niche. In addition, *in vitro* neurosphere cultures from MSG-injured brain (i.e, *ex vivo*) showed an intriguing priming effect of the lesion on NPCs proliferation. This pro-neurogenic effect can be correlated with NPCs oxygen consumption, suggestion that microenvironment changes promoted by neuronal cell death determines significant and long-lasting plasticity of NPCs metabolism.

Presentation I:

Title:

The Role Of Structural Plasticity In Huntington's Disease.

Joana Gil-Mohapel, Ph.D.¹, Jessica Simpson, M.Sc.¹, Mohamed Ghilan, Ph.D.¹, Brian R. Christie, PhD.¹, and Patricia S. Brocardo, Ph.D.² ¹Island Medical Program, Faculty of Medicine, University of British Columbia and Division of Medical Sciences, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, Canada; ²Department of Morphological Sciences, Center of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil; ³Department of Biochemistry, Center of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil

Abstract:

Increasing evidence over the last 50 years has demonstrated that the mammalian brain retains the capacity to generate new neurons throughout adulthood through a process referred to as adult neurogenesis, a form of structural plasticity. This capacity is restricted to well-defined brain regions, including the sub-granular zone (SGZ) of the hippocampal dentate gyrus (DG). In addition, various forms of short- and long-term synaptic plasticity also occur in the hippocampus. Importantly, the hippocampus is thought to play a role in certain aspects of cognition including learning and memory, and both structural (i.e., generation of new neurons) and synaptic plasticity is thought to contribute to these processes. As such, it is believed that neurodegenerative conditions associated with impaired cognition, such as Huntington's disease (HD), may be associated with altered hippocampal neurogenic function and synaptic plasticity. In this symposium I will present an overview of the evidence implicating a dysregulation of hippocampal neurogenesis and synaptic plasticity in various transgenic models of HD (the R6/2 and the YAC128 HD transgenic mice). Of note, these deficits can be detected early on in both models, prior to the development of the classical motor symptoms of the disease, thus providing a neuropathological correlate to the early-onset cognitive disturbances observed in these transgenic mice as well as in human HD patients. Since adult neural progenitors have been proposed as an endogenous source of healthy neurons, I will also discuss possible strategies to harness the endogenous

neurogenic capacity in the HD brain, which might be of therapeutic value for treatment of the cognitive deficits associated with this devastating neurodegenerative disease.

Presentation II:

Title:

Neuroprotection by modulation of hippocampal neurogenesis: potential therapeutic effects in models of depression and stress.

Joana Gil-Mohapel, Ph.D.¹, Luis E. B. Bettio, Ph.D.¹, Francis L. Pazini, M.Sc.², Gislaine Olescowicz², Brian R. Christie, PhD.¹, Patricia S. Brocardo, Ph.D.³, and Ana Lucia S. Rodrigues, Ph.D.² ¹Island Medical Program, Faculty of Medicine, University of British Columbia and Division of Medical Sciences, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, Canada; ²Department of Biochemistry, Center of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil; ³Department of Morphological Sciences, Center of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil.

Abstract:

Adult neurogenesis plays a significant role in hippocampal-dependent functions, particularly in the modulation of cognitive and affective processes. Since this form of plasticity is impaired in various neurological and psychiatric conditions, such as depression and stress, the search for compounds that can potentiate hippocampal neurogenesis and reverse the behavioural deficits observed in animal models of depression and stress, while also resulting in minimal side effects, is a recognized priority. Within this context and given their well established neuroprotective properties, we have recently tested the potential of guanosine, creatine, and agmatine in promoting hippocampal neurogenic function and reducing the occurrence of depressive-like behaviours in rodent models of depression and stress. These three compounds were able to potentiate adult hippocampal neurogenesis while also reducing the occurrence of depressive-like behaviours, thus highlighting the neuroprotective properties of these compounds and further supporting their use as neuromodulators for the treatment of affective disorders associated with depressive-like symptoms. In addition, we have also tested the pro-neurogenic effects of isoxazole 9 (Isx-9), a small synthetic molecule that has been recently identified through the screening of chemical libraries in stem cell-based assays. Of note, we found that Isx-9 is able to reverse the deleterious effects of stress (repeated restraint stress and chronic unpredictable stress) on hippocampal neurogenesis by potentiating cell proliferation and increasing the number of

immature neurons in the hippocampal dentate gyrus of adult rats. These findings indicate that Isx-9 is a promising synthetic compound for the treatment of conditions associated with deficits in hippocampal neurogenesis, such as chronic exposure to stress.

Presentation:

Title:

Delaying Aging and Improving Metabolism with Drugs that Target miRNA Biogenesis.

Marcelo A. Mori, IB/UNICAMP

Abstract:

Dietary restriction creates a negative energy balance that improves metabolic control at the level of the cell and the organism. In turn, these changes delay aging and increase lifespan in organisms across the evolutionary spectrum. Studies from our group and others placed miRNAs as key determinants of the beneficial outcomes of dietary restriction. Taken these studies into consideration, we designed experiments to test whether pharmacological interventions capable of affecting miRNA biogenesis have an impact on aging and metabolism across species. We identified a class of drugs (i.e. fluoroquinolones) that mimic dietary restriction in *C. elegans* and mice by interfering with the miRNA processing pathway. In worms, these drugs increase lifespan, delay age-related dysfunction, and protect from oxidative and proteotoxic stress. In mice, fluoroquinolones protect from diet-induced obesity by promoting beige adipocyte recruitment and increasing energy expenditure. Importantly, the drugs act by down-regulating miR-34 in both mice and worms. This mechanism appears to involve double-stranded RNA-specific adenosine deaminases and a switch in *pre-miR-34* arm bias. Given the conserved characteristics of the phenomenon, we expect this mechanism to be extrapolated to humans to which fluoroquinolones have been widely prescribed.

Presentation:

Title:

Valproic acid effects on chromatin epigenetic marks.

Maria Luiza S. Mello

IB, Department of Structural and Functional Biology, Unicamp, Campinas, SP

Abstract:

Valproic acid, a drug classically used for treatment of epileptic outbreaks, acts on different kinds of epigenetic marks through mechanisms that vary, depending on cell types and their physiological/pathological conditions. Its effects comprise not only interference on levels of histone acetylation, through inhibition of histone deacetylases and predominant induction of H3K9 and H4K8 acetylation, but also DNA demethylation and histone methylation and/or demethylation. With regard to DNA demethylation, this process may follow active or passive pathways or even both. As a result from the different metabolic pathways of the valproic acid action, consequences are expressed at the chromatin structural and functional levels, and on differential gene expression. We are learning that various different effects promoted by the valproic acid on chromatin may occur simultaneously, thus revealing how complex and entangled are the metabolic pathways involved. The basic scientific knowledge raised in this realm is relevant for the judicious evaluation of using valproic acid in clinical trials and so that advancement of new therapeutic proposals using this or similar drugs could be made. Some of our results particularly addressed to HeLa cells and a glioblastoma cell line will be presented as a contribution to visualization of changes in epigenetic marks induced by valproic acid.

Sponsor: FAPESP (Thematic Project: 2015/10356-2)

Presentation:

Title:

Investigating the role of the Δ TG mutation in *XPC* gene on expression of the transcriptional co-activator PGC-1 α .

Mateus Prates Mori e Nadja Cristhina de Souza-Pinto.

Instituto de Química, Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo.

Abstract:

Xeroderma pigmentosum (XP) is an inherited autosomal recessive syndrome with a 1,000 fold elevated skin cancer rate in areas exposed to UV light. XP is caused by mutations in one of seven genes (*XPA-XPG*) of nucleotide excision repair (NER) pathway or in one translesion DNA polymerase (*POLH*). The XPC protein is a lesion recognition factor in NER, but it has also been shown to interact and stimulate DNA glycosylases OGG1, TDG and SMUG1, to act as transcriptional co-activator and on energy metabolism adaptation. Using XP-C cells we have recently demonstrated that these cells show increased mitochondrial H₂O₂ production with an adaptive shift between respiratory complexes I and II, leading to increased sensibility towards mitochondrial stress. A surprising finding was a very significant decrease in expression of the transcriptional coactivator PGC-1 α (*PPARGC1A*), which has a major role in controlling mitochondrial biogenesis. In four different XP-C cell lines tested, reduction of *PPARGC1A* expression was detected in three, all of them carrying the c.1643_1644delTG mutation (Δ TG) in *XPC*. In an XP-C cell line carrying a different mutation, we did not observed a reduction of *PPARGC1A* expression, regardless of nearly absent XPC protein levels, in agreement with results showing that siRNA-mediated XPC knockdown did not alter *PPARGC1A* expression. Results from other genetic diseases suggest that some mutations can generate new non-coding RNA, with a gain-of-function new molecular phenotype. In this context we propose to investigate: i) the correlation between the Δ TG mutation and *PPARGC1A* expression, expanding the investigation towards other mutations in *XPC*; ii) the possible epigenetic regulation of this repression; iii) the functional consequences resulting from this possible association between Δ TG mutation and the repression of *PPARGC1A* expression.

Presentation:

Title:

SIRT1 regulates *Mxd1* throughout melanoma progression.

Fabiana M. Meliso, Danilo Micali, Camila T. Silva, Thaís S. Sabedot, Simon G. Coetzee, Adrian Koch, Fabian B. Fahlbusch, Houtan Noushmehr, Regine Schneider-Stock, Miriam G. Jasiulionis; Dept. Farmacologia, UNIFESP.

Abstract:

In a murine melanoma model of malignant transformation promoted by sustained stress, increased levels of reactive oxygen species were found to result in DNA damage and were related to massive epigenetic alterations. Since the chromatin modifier Sirtuin-1 (SIRT1) is a protein attracted to double-stranded DNA break (DSB) sites and can recruit other components of the epigenetic machinery, we aimed to define the role of SIRT1 in melanomagenesis through our melanoma model. The DNA damage marker, γ H2AX was found increased in melanocytes after 24 hours of deadhesion, accompanied by increased SIRT1 expression and decreased levels of its target, H4K16ac. Moreover, SIRT1 started to be associated to DNMT3B during the stress condition, and this complex was maintained along malignant progression. *Mxd1* was identified by ChIP-seq among the DNA sequences differentially associated with SIRT1 during deadhesion and was shown to be a common target of both, SIRT1 and DNMT3B. In addition, *Mxd1* was found down-regulated from pre-malignant melanocytes to metastatic melanoma cells. Treatment with DNMT inhibitor 5AzaCdR reversed the *Mxd1* expression. *Sirt1* stable silencing increased *Mxd1* mRNA expression and led to up-regulation of MYC targets, such as *Cdkn1a*, *Bcl2* and *Psen2*, the upregulation of which is associated with human melanoma aggressiveness and poor prognosis. We demonstrated a novel role of the stress responsive protein SIRT1 in malignant transformation of melanocytes associated with deadhesion. *Mxd1* was identified as a new SIRT1 target gene. SIRT1 promoted *Mxd1* silencing, which led to increased activity of MYC oncogene contributing to melanoma progression. Supported by FAPESP, CAPES and CNPq.

Presentation:

Title:

Antidepressant effects of probucol in early-symptomatic YAC128 Huntington's disease transgenic mice.

Patrícia de Souza Brocardo, UFSC

Abstract:

Huntington's disease (HD) is an autosomal dominant neurodegenerative disorder caused by a trinucleotide expansion in the HD gene, resulting in an extended polyglutamine tract in the protein huntingtin (HTT). HD has traditionally been considered a movement disorder, but cognitive and psychiatric symptoms are also important into its clinical presentation. Depression is one of the most common psychiatric disturbances in HD, present even before manifestation of motor symptoms. Identification and treatment of depression in individuals with the HD mutation is an essential part of clinical management in this population, especially owing to the high risk of suicide. In this study, asymptomatic and early symptomatic YAC128 mice (transgenic animal model of HD) received probucol, a lipid-lowering phenolic compound with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, in the drinking water, beginning on the 1st month of their life until they completed 6 month old. The depressive phenotype was completely rescued in YAC128 animals by chronic treatment with probucol. However, these effects were not related to proliferation or differentiation of new neurons in the dentate gyrus (DG) hippocampal region.

Presentation:

Title:

Dual effect of local melatonin synthesized and exogenous melatonin in the selective protection of the cerebellum against intracerebroventricular (icv) LPS.

Regina P. Markus, Laboratory of Chronopharmacology, Institute of Bioscience, USP.

Abstract:

Melatonin, an indolamine derived from the acetylation and sequential methylation of serotonin is well-known as the hormone of darkness. Indeed, a nocturnal peak of melatonin marks darkness in plants and animals. In mammals, the pineal gland is the responsible for daily melatonin rhythm in blood and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Melatonin synthesis is triggered by direct projection of retina ganglion cells to the suprachiasmatic nuclei, hypothalamic paraventricular nuclei, spinal cord sympathetic output and pineal gland. Melatonin is immediately released both in the circulation and CSF and is efficiently metabolized by CYPs (cytochrome P450 enzymes) both in the liver and in the brain. Therefore, as soon as pineal melatonin synthesis is stopped by environmental lighting the levels in blood and CSF drops. Therefore, the basal/signal ratio is optimized for translating environmental lighting. Melatonin is also constitutively synthesized in the guts and testes, where it exerts protective effects, and monocytes/macrophages/microglia and lymphocyte melatonin synthesis is induced by defense responses. A systemic evaluation of the relationship between pineal and immune competent cells induction of melatonin leads to the confirmation of the Immune-Pineal Axis. The mounting of an inflammatory response includes the suppression of nocturnal melatonin synthesis, allowing the migration to the injured area, and the synthesis of melatonin by activated immune competent cells. Lipopolysaccharide (LPS, icv) injection in rats reduces the nocturnal peak of melatonin in the plasma and induces its synthesis in the cerebellum, though not in the cortex or hippocampus. Cerebellar melatonin synthesis requires the activation of nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), which positively regulates the expression of arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AA-NAT). LPS induces neuronal death in the hippocampus and cortex, but not in the cerebellum. This privileged protection of cerebellar cells was abrogated when melatonin receptors were blocked by luzindole. The treatment of cultured cerebellar cells with melatonin present a dual effect. In the presence of LPS, the protective effect was observed, and it was due to

inhibition of NF- κ B and reduction of NO. Otherwise, in naïve cells, melatonin promotes cell death, as in the specific case of cerebellar cultures a constitutive activation of NF- κ B and NO synthesis is essential for neuronal surviving. Interestingly, in glioma cells in culture, the two subtypes of melatonin receptors have opposite effects regarding cell proliferation. Therefore, both local synthesized and exogenous melatonin are neuroprotective against neuroinflammation, but the understanding of melatonin effect in normal conditions need further investigation.

Financial support: FAPESP (2013/13691-1; 2007/078716; CNPq 480097/2013-5).

Presentation:

Title:

Epigenetic biomarkers and resilience as a key to predict relapse in drug addictions treatment.

Rubens Harb Bollos, UNIFESP

Abstract:

The use of psychoactive substances have been used in humanity since the earliest times, including alcohol. Dependence is a chronic, debilitating and progressive psychiatric disorder and brain disease characterized by compulsive, abusive drug demand and consumption that can lead to the harmful behaviors. Drug addiction is now a public and collective health problem that involves factors: 1) genetic, which attempt to explain individual differences to drug responsiveness; and 2) epigenetic, which would contribute to individual sensitivity to environmental effects, that include biopsychosocial factors besides cultural and economic factors. Once an individual becomes addicted, there are few effective clinical options and relapses are common. The focus of the lesson will be on relapses: how to identify them? In a retrospective study, patients with alcohol dependence under treatment and followed up on their outcomes and relapses were investigated. Epigenetic circulating factors in the serum of these patients were analyzed. Neurocognitive assessments were measured using the human resilience scale, the sense of coherence that focuses attention on the personal protective resources that help the person overcome the difficulties that arise in their life, sustaining their individual health. The results of relapse rates were correlated with epigenetic factors and human resilience. And a predictive profile of vulnerability with respect to relapse in drug addiction was proposed.

Presentation I:**Title:**

In vitro screening platforms in mammalian cells to identify autophagy modulators for therapeutic interventions in neurodegenerative disorders.

Sovan Sarkar

Institute of Cancer and Genomic Sciences, Institute of Biomedical Research, College of Medical and Dental Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom

Abstract:

Autophagy is a vital homeostatic pathway essential for cellular survival and human health. It primarily functions as an intracellular degradation process for the turnover of aggregation-prone proteins and unwanted organelles. Dysregulation of autophagy underlying diverse human diseases reduces cell viability whereas stimulation of autophagy is cytoprotective in a number of transgenic disease models including neurodegenerative disorders. Thus, therapeutic exploitation of autophagy is considered a potential treatment strategy in certain human diseases, and therefore, chemical inducers of autophagy have tremendous biomedical relevance. A number of *in vitro* screening platforms have been established to identify autophagy modulators in mammalian cells using various methodologies including fluorescence and high-content imaging, flow cytometry, fluorescence and luminescence detection by microplate reader, immunoblotting and immunofluorescence. The commonly-used autophagy reporters in these screening platforms are either based on autophagy marker like LC3 or autophagy substrate such as aggregation-prone proteins or p62/SQSTM1. The reporters and assays for monitoring autophagy are evolving over time to become more sensitive in measuring autophagic flux with the capability of high-throughput applications for drug discovery. In this talk, these developments will be highlighted along with the stringent secondary autophagy assays for characterizing the autophagy modulators arising from the primary screen. Since autophagy is implicated in myriad human physiological and pathological conditions, these technologies will enable identifying novel chemical modulators or genetic regulators of autophagy that will be of biomedical and fundamental importance to human health.

Presentation II:**Title:**

Targeting autophagy dysfunction in rare childhood neurodegenerative diseases as a common pathway for therapeutic interventions.

Sovan Sarkar

Institute of Cancer and Genomic Sciences, Institute of Biomedical Research, College of Medical and Dental Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom

Abstract:

Autophagy is essential for cellular survival and organismal health. Deregulation of this homeostatic process leads to myriad human diseases including neurodegeneration. We aim to study the role of autophagy in rare, childhood neurodegenerative diseases by generating disease-relevant human cellular platforms with phenotypic readouts. Our goal is to establish defective autophagy as a shared mechanism in these conditions for targeting this common pathway for therapeutic intervention. Previously, we described dysfunctional autophagy in Niemann-Pick type C1 (NPC1) disease, an early-onset neurodegenerative lysosomal storage disorder, by establishing disease-relevant phenotypes in induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived neurons. In this patient-derived disease-affected cellular platform, autophagy inducers were cytoprotective by restoring functional autophagic flux. We are currently studying the role of autophagy in Wolfram syndrome (WS), a rare, monogenic form of childhood neurodegenerative disease. In immortalized neuronal cells and patient fibroblasts of WS, autophagosome biogenesis was suppressed that consequently retarded autophagic flux and mitophagy. This was associated with alterations in mitochondrial function and calcium homeostasis. Importantly, increased cell death in WS cell models was rescued by small-molecule autophagy inducers. Using WS patient-derived iPSC model, we are currently developing the disease-affected neuronal platform to establish defective autophagy and cell death as phenotypic readouts for drug screening. Our data suggest impaired autophagic flux in WS where treatment with autophagy inducers was cytoprotective, and a role of WFS1 protein in regulating autophagosome biogenesis. In a nutshell, establishing defective autophagy in rare, childhood neurodegenerative diseases as a shared pathological mechanism could be targeted for a unifying treatment strategy.

Presentation:

Title:

Mitochondrial dysfunction as a consequence of hypoxia, and their role to the development of Schizophrenia.

Sousa e Silva LF¹, Dutra MB¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Department of Physiological Science, Santa Casa de São Paulo School of Medical Sciences, São Paulo

Abstract:

The objective of this work is to evaluate mitochondrial function in different models of Schizophrenia (SHZ) as a consequence of hypoxia: astrocytes from spontaneously hypertensive rat (SHR), astrocytes exposed to cobalt chloride (CoCl₂) and cells incubated in hypoxia chamber (0% oxygen). It was analyzed the following parameters: cytosolic Ca²⁺ (cCa²⁺) levels (with Fluo-4 AM [10μM]), mitochondria membrane potential (ΔΨ_m) (using TMRE [500 nM]), reactive oxygen species levels (ROS) (with DCF [20 μM]) and oxygen consumption (O₂nmol/mL/min); the results were analyzed as a percentage of the control group. We can observe that the mitochondria of the SHR astrocytes accumulate more Ca²⁺ since they have lower basal cytosolic fluorescence (W: 100% ±5 x SHR: 85% ±1,97) and an increase of it as a consequence of FCCP addition. Moreover, SHR astrocytes are depolarized in relation to the CTR group (W: 100% ±3,6 x SHR: 115% ±5,8), presents higher levels of ROS (W: 100% ±12,6 x SHR: 123% ±5) and also shows an increase in oxygen consumption (O₂nmol/mL/min) (W= 6,9 x SHR: 22). The treatment with CoCl₂ (800 μM and 2 mM) was able to induce alterations in CTR and SHR cells namely: 1) diminish of cCa²⁺ in Wistar and SHR rats; 2) augmentation of ΔΨ_m in Wistar and SHR astrocytes; 3) increase in ROS in Wistar cells, but not in SHR group; 4) a significant intensification of oxygen consumption in Wistar and SHR cells. In order to correlate the data obtained with cells exposed to the hypoxia chamber, astrocytes were incubated with 0% oxygen for 8, 18 and 24 hours. We observed that 1) hypoxia induced a decrease in cCa²⁺ in a time-dependent manner, 2) hypoxia induces mitochondrial depolarization in both groups, but SHR seems to be more sensitive just after long periods without O₂, and 3) hypoxia induces an increase in ROS levels after 8 hrs, but not in longer periods; SHR cells seems to be more resistant to the production of ROS due to oxygen levels. Therefore, we conclude that hypoxia seems to be the central mechanisms responsible for mitochondrial dysfunction that can lead, as a consequence, cellular changes resembling features and symptoms of Schizophrenia.

Financial Support: FAPESP, CAPES e CNPq

Presentation I:

Title:

Redefining Neurodegenerative Diseases through Epigenetics.

Tiago Fleming Outeiro, University Medical Center Goettingen, Germany

Abstract:

Neurodegenerative disorders, such as Alzheimer's (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD), are highly complex conditions that affect a growing number of patients worldwide, due to the aging of the human population. These disorders have a multifactorial origin, depending not only on genetic but also on environmental factors. Several genetic risk factors have already been associated with both AD and PD, but the precise mechanisms through which the environment contributes to neurodegeneration are still unclear. Recently, epigenetic mechanisms, such as DNA methylation, chromatin remodelling or miRNAs, which induce alterations in gene expression, have been implicated in various neurodegenerative conditions. Given that epigenetic modulation is present from pre-natal stages and throughout life, and that it depends on lifestyle conditions and environmental factors, it might provide new insights into the molecular basis of neurodegeneration, opening novel avenues for therapeutic intervention.

Presentation II:

Title:

Unravelling the Role of Posttranslational Modifications on Alpha-Synuclein Biology and Pathobiology.

Tiago Fleming Outeiro, University Medical Center Goettingen, Germany

Abstract:

The aggregation of alpha-synuclein (ASYN) in Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites is the typical pathological hallmark of Parkinson's disease (PD) and other synucleinopathies. Furthermore, mutations in the gene encoding for ASYN are associated with familial and sporadic forms of PD, suggesting this protein plays a central role in the disease. However, the precise contribution of ASYN to neuronal dysfunction and death is still unclear. There is intense debate on the nature of the toxic species of ASYN, and little is still known about the molecular determinants of oligomerization and aggregation of ASYN in the cell. By taking advantage of studies in model organisms, we are investigating the effect of various posttranslational modifications on the toxicity and aggregation of ASYN. We found that glycation and acetylation are emerging as important modifications affecting ASYN aggregation. In addition, we are also defining the molecular mechanisms triggered by extracellular forms of ASYN, a process associated with the spreading of pathology. In total, our data shed light into the molecular underpinnings of synucleinopathies, opening novel perspectives for future therapeutic interventions.

Resumos Apresentações Alunos

Presentation:

Title:

NEONATAL COBALT CHLORIDE TREATMENT INCREASES LOCOMOTOR ACTIVITY IN YOUNG AND ADULTS RATS – PARTICIPATION OF DOPAMINERGIC TRANSMISSION

Ramos, AC¹; Suiama, MA²; Derci, N²; Rosenstock, TR³; Calzavara, MB¹ - ¹Department of Psychiatry – UNIFESP; ²Department of Pharmacology – UNIFESP; ³Department of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP

Abstract:

Increased striatal release of dopamine is associated with hiperlocomotion in animal models and this paradigm is frequently used to understand psychiatric diseases. Knowing that dopaminergic system is vulnerable to hypoxic insults, we investigated the effects of treating rats with cobalt chloride (CoCl₂) – a compound that produces chemical hypoxia – on locomotor behavior. Animals were treated at postnatal day 7 (PND 7) – a critic period to brain development - and the effects were observed at day 50 (PND 50 - young) and 90 (PND90 - adults). After that, rats were acutely treated with antipsychotic haloperidol – a D2 receptor blocker – seeking out to reverse the alterations caused by CoCl₂ exposure. Animals treated with CoCl₂ in perinatal period showed hiperlocomotion when young (CTR: 93.5; CC: 145.6; p= 0.03) and adults (CTR: 59.63; CC: 100.1; p= 0.005). This alterations were reversed by haloperidol in both periods (YOUNG – CC: 103.0; HAL: 21.25; p= 0.003. ADULTS – CC: 126.5; HAL: 28.25; p= 0.003). During the neurodevelopment phase, CoCl₂-induced hypoxia promotes hiperlocomotion, which is reversed by haloperidol-induced D2 blockade . These data suggest that hypoxia leads to a dopaminergic hyperactivity which can be pharmacologically reversed approximating this model to what is suggested to occur in the pathophysiology of schizophrenia.

Presentation:**Title:**

THE INVOLVEMENT OF MITOCHONDRIAL DYSFUNCTION IN NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS: A BEHAVIORAL APPROACH/STUDY.

Siena A¹, Yukawa JM¹, Ramos AC², Da Silva EC¹, Torresi JLB¹, Brito MD¹, Silva LFS¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Departament of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP; ²Departament of Pharmacology – UNIFESP

Abstract:

The aim of this study was to evaluate the involvement of mitochondrial dysfunction in behavioral alterations related to neurodevelopmental disorders. For reach this goal, we treated wistar puppies rats (P) from P5 to P11 with Rotenone (Rot., 0,1 e 0,5 mg/kg), a complex I inhibitor, and Saline and DMSO (control groups). The animals were also treated from P5 to P7 with Rot. 1,0 mg/kg. The mitochondrial respiration was evaluated at P12, P30, P60 and P120, and the behavioral tests were performed in rats at P60 and P120. Results show a decrease in mitochondrial respiration rate after treatment with Rot. 1,0 mg/kg at P12 (68,75%±10,34) and Rot. 0,1mg/kg (27,67%±7,641) and Rot. 0,5mg/kg (41,64%±6,517), both at P30, when compared to control group (100%). No changes were found at P60 and P120 regarding oxygen consumption. Concomitantly, when compared to control group (100%), we have observed: i) an increase in locomotor activity at P60 and P120 after treatments with Rot. 0,1mg/kg (P60: 138%±7,99; P120:129,95%±8,25), Rot. 0,5mg/kg (P60:125,6%±7,27; P120:136,51%±9,15) and Rot. 1,0mg/kg (P60:134,54%±8,08; P120:135,55%±15,05); ii) a decrease in social interaction at P60 after treatments with Rot. 0,1mg/kg (69,63%±7,93), Rot.0,5mg/kg (50,21%±4,05) and Rot. 1,0mg/kg (75,18%±5,07), and at P120, only after Rot. 0,1mg/kg (72,91%±9,32); and iii) a deficit on fear conditioning context only after treatment with Rot. 0,1mg/kg (38,55%±10,69). We conclude that the lowest dose of Rotenone can cause behavior deficits along age, suggesting a possible neuronal modulation that can culminate in neurodevelopmental disorders.

Presentation:**Title:**

Perfil termorregulatório alterado em ratos Wistar adultos submetidos à Separação Materna.

Melo, C.; Ugeda, N.; Ishikawa, D.; Echeverry, M.B.; Carrettiero, D.; Almeida, M.C. (UFABC)

Abstract:

Resumo: Sabe-se que pacientes com depressão apresentam disfunções nos mecanismos de termorregulação. Nós avaliamos o perfil termorregulatório de ratos Wistar submetidos à separação materna (SM). Animais SM apresentaram maior temperatura corporal no período escuro, hipertermia durante a exposição ao calor e optaram por temperaturas ambiente mais baixas quando comparados aos controles, sugerindo uma mudança no perfil termorregulatório de ratos SM.

Objetivos: Geral: Avaliar o perfil termorregulatório de ratos Wistar submetidos à separação materna (SM). Específicos: Verificar a influência da SM na temperatura corporal de ratos adultos, bem como as respostas termorregulatórias de defesa durante a exposição ao frio (10°C) e ao calor (32°C), e no comportamento durante a seleção de temperatura ambiente.

Métodos: Após o nascimento, os ratos Wistar foram divididos randomicamente em dois grupos: experimental e controle. No grupo experimental a SM foi realizada das 9h às 12h, do dia pós-natal 2 ao 14. Após o período de separação, os filhotes foram devolvidos às suas respectivas e mães, e o desmame realizado depois de 21 dias do nascimento. Os experimentos foram realizados em ratos adultos, com aproximadamente 12 semanas de idade. Apenas os machos foram utilizados nos experimentos deste estudo. Cada rato recebeu um dispositivo para registro da temperatura corporal (SubCue Dataloggers, Calgary, AB, Canada) na cavidade peritoneal em procedimento cirúrgico de laparotomia mediana. Para confirmar os efeitos comportamentais da SM foram realizados os experimentos: campo aberto, labirinto em cruz elevado, interação social e natação forçada. Os testes termorregulatórios

incluíram: medição de temperatura corporal durante 24 horas (sem nenhuma interferência), resposta na exposição ao frio e ao calor, e seleção de temperatura ambiente.

Resultados: No teste de campo aberto, os animais SM percorreram uma distância maior ($P < 0.05$), permaneceram um tempo menor no centro do aparato ($P < 0.05$), além de apresentarem menos comportamentos exploratórios ($P < 0.001$) e mais *grooming* ($P < 0.05$) em relação aos controles. Quando expostos ao labirinto em cruz elevado, o grupo SM permaneceu menor tempo nos braços abertos do aparato ($P = 0.001$). Não foram observadas diferenças estatísticas na interação social. No teste de natação forçada, o grupo SM apresentou um número maior de eventos de imobilidade ($P < 0.001$) e um menor número de eventos de escalada ($P < 0.001$). A temperatura corporal foi significativamente maior durante o período escuro ($P < 0.05$) nos ratos SM. Além disso, os animais SM apresentaram hipertermia em resposta ao calor quando comparados aos controles ($P < 0.05$). Após a exposição ao frio, os animais SM apresentaram uma ligeira resposta hipertérmica ($P < 0.05$). No teste de seleção de temperatura, animais SM permaneceram maior período em temperaturas mais frias em relação aos controles ($P < 0.001$, $P = 0.048$), e realizaram mais *grooming* ($P < 0.05$).

Discussão e Conclusão: Nos testes comportamentais, os animais SM apresentaram mais comportamentos de ansiedade e menos comportamentos de exploração, confirmando a efetividade do modelo de SM para proporcionar sintomas relacionados à depressão e à ansiedade. Nos testes termorregulatórios, os animais SM não apenas apresentaram deficiência nos mecanismos de resfriamento, como também apresentaram um atraso na ativação / desativação dos mecanismos termorregulatórios. O aumento da temperatura corporal nos pacientes com depressão é observado e aceito como uma disfunção no mecanismo termorregulatório de resfriamento e pode até mesmo reduzir a transpiração em indivíduos saudáveis. Nossos resultados sugerem que os animais SM apresentam alterações no perfil termorregulatório com aumento de temperatura corporal durante o período ativo (escuro), deficiência na defesa de sua temperatura corporal contra o calor, um atraso na desativação da resposta de defesa ao frio e uma preferência por temperaturas ambiente mais frias em relação aos animais controles.

Presentation:

Title:

ALTERAÇÕES DE PADRÕES COMPORTAMENTAIS E FUNÇÃO MITOCONDRIAL EM PACIENTES DE ALTO RISCO PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DA ESQUIZOFRENIA (PRÓDROMOS): UMA POSSÍVEL IDENTIFICAÇÃO DE BIOMARCADORES.

Ruiz DPP¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Departament of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP.

Abstract:

O objetivo do projeto que será apresentado é realizar um estudo caso-coorte com amostras obtidas do ambulatório da Universidade Federal de São Paulo (UNIFESP), especificamente do Programa de Reconhecimento e Intervenção nos Estados Mentais de Risco (PRISMA) do visando caracterizar o perfil dos pacientes em alto risco clínico para desenvolver esquizofrenia e determinar progressivamente as relações causais, verificar e estabelecer a presença de padrões comportamentais e moleculares de grupo controle e dois grupos experimentais, grupo em alto risco clínico para desenvolver esquizofrenia e grupo já diagnosticado com esquizofrenia. Desta forma, estabeleceria uma relação causal entre os parâmetros comportamentais como movimento ocular, reconhecimento de emoções, valência afetiva, memória verbal e previsibilidade semântica juntamente com os dados moleculares como as disfunções mitocondriais quanto aos níveis de estresse oxidativo, potencial de membrana mitocondrial, consumo de oxigênio, níveis e expressão de proteínas, fatores de transcrição relacionados com o metabolismo energético, ainda serão determinados do número de cópias do DNA mitocondrial e medição dos níveis de ATP/ADP, Piruvato/Lactato e NAD⁺/NADH. Assim mapeando a progressão do desenvolvimento da SHZ e a indicação de potenciais biomarcadores para intervenções precoces e terapêuticas.

Presentation:

Title:

AGE-RELATED MITOCHONDRIAL METABOLISM EVALUATION AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH NEURAL FUNCTION IN AN ANIMAL MODEL OF SCHIZOPHRENIA.

Silva EH¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Department of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP.

Abstract:

Among all theories related to the neuropathological features of Schizophrenia (SHZ), we can highlight the Neuroprogression Theory. Regarding to it, cellular changes, such as modifications in neural proliferation, cellular migration and differentiation, as well as variations in the synapse formation, would be increased for sequential psychotic crisis and absence of medical guidance, leading to a degenerative process (cell death). Considering that all processes mentioned above and even the synaptic transmission relies on energetic demand (ATP production), the maintenance of mitochondrial metabolism is essential for neural regulation and survival. Therefore, the goal of this project is to evaluate, concomitantly, mitochondrial and neural function in a pathognomonic animal model of SHZ, SHR rats (*Spontaneous Hypertensive rats*), along aging, as well as evaluate behavioral changes and its progression. Indeed, the usage of SHR with different ages (2, 4, 6 and 9 months of age) will help to identify metabolic alteration even before the onset of schizophrenia-like symptoms that, in this animal strain, start around 4 months. Thus, the relevance of this study is that we believe it will be possible to identify cellular metabolic alterations and correlate them to neural modification and, as a result, understand how these factors influence cellular viability and the progression of SHZ. We also expect that this project, at a middle-long term, help in the acquirement of a laboratorial tool, such as a biomarker, to be applied together with clinical indexes, in the follow-up of this psychiatric disorder.

Presentation:

Title:

MODULATION OF MITOCHONDRIAL FUNCTION AND DEGRADATION BY LYSINE-DEACETYLASES AFTER OVEREXPRESSION AND SUPPRESSION OF GENES RELATED TO AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS.

Tilieri EM¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Departament of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP.

Abstract:

Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the progressive loss of motor neurons. Despite the fact that 90% of ALS cases are sporadic, part of it (10%) is due to genetic reasons (ALSf). However, up to now, ALS etiology is multifactorial, since it does not only present changes in genic expression and an increase in misfolded proteins inclusion and oxidative stress, but also modifications in mitochondrial function and degradation. Importantly, ALS does not have cure, and, as a consequence, one of the main concerns is to develop neuroprotective strategies. In fact, one of the most promising approaches is the epigenetic modification, in which acetylation of lysine (K) is highlighted. Once lysine (K)-deacetylases (KDACs) regulate proteins enrolled in several processes named genetic transcription, cellular degradation and metabolism, in which mitochondria plays an important role, the goal of this project is to evaluate mitochondrial function and mitophagy in nervous cells after changes in the expression of genes related to ALSf (*Sod1*, *C9orf72* e *p62*), as well as the role of KDAC modulation over these mechanisms and its neuroprotective effect. To reach this objective, distinct experiments will be performed in order to evaluate mitochondrial metabolism, dynamic and degradation in astrocytes. Therefore, the importance of this study is the fact that it will be define the relevance of the most common genes related to ALSf to mitochondrial function and degradation, and how KDACs could lead to neuroprotection, through mitophagy, in the most abundant brain cell type.

Presentation:

Title:

THE EFFECT OF CANNABINOID RECEPTOR 1 (CB1) SELECTIVE AGONIST ON MODELS OF STREPTOZOTOCIN-INDUCED NEURODEGENERATION.

CRUNFLI, F.1; VRECHI, T.A.M.2; COSTA, A.P.3; TORRÃO, A.S.3

1 *Dept. Pharmacology, School of Medicine of Ribeirão Preto- University of São Paulo* Brazil, Ribeirão Preto, SP, Brazil.; 2 *Dept. Pharmacology, Institute of Cellular Pharmacology and Biology, Federal University of São Paulo, São Paulo, SP, Brazil;* 3 *Dept. Physiology and Biophysics, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, SP, Brazil.*

Abstract:

Several studies have demonstrated the involvement of cannabinoid system in neurodegenerative processes like Alzheimer Disease's (AD) and suggested its neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties. The cannabinoid system has the ability to modulate cellular mechanisms, by its relationship with signaling pathways associated to the control of cell proliferation, differentiation and survival. AD is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the presence of amyloid plaques, neurofibrillary tangles, neuronal death and progressive cognitive loss. Advanced age is one of the major risk factors of sporadic AD and it associated with energy metabolism impairment and changes in insulin signaling in the brain. In this context, low doses of intracerebroventricular (icv) injection of streptozotocin (STZ) in rodents has been used as an experimental model of sAD which leads to an insulin-resistant brain state and neurodegeneration. Thus, we investigated the protective effect of the cannabinoid type 1 (CB1)-selective receptor agonist arachidonyl-2'-chloroethylamide (ACEA) against STZ exposure stimuli in an *in vitro* model (Neuro2a neuroblastoma cells) and *in vivo* model (icv STZ injection on Wistar rats male - Protocol n°54/19/03). ACEA treatment reversed cognitive impairment caused by STZ; increased IR expression, and reversed the increased of Akt and ERK activity caused by STZ. Moreover, ACEA treatment increased the Bcl-2 levels antiapoptotic proteins. The exposure of Neuro 2a cells to STZ decreased the cell viability and ACEA was able to rescue the cells from death. In addition, ACEA treatment reversed the increase in STZ-released nitrite, indicating that ACEA could modulate the release of NO. Our data suggest that the cannabinoid system is an interesting therapeutic target for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases.

Presentation:

Title:

AVALIAÇÃO DA EXPRESSÃO DE C-FOS NO NÚCLEO PARABRAQUIAL LATERAL E ÁREA PRÉ-ÓPTICA DO HIPOTÁLAMO EM RESPOSTA AO TRATAMENTO CRÔNICO COM MENTOL.

Giovana Marchini Armentano, Robson Cristiano Lillo Vizin, Sonia Guerrero Pietro, Marcela Bermudez Echeverry, Daniel C. Carrettiero, Maria Camila Almeida; Universidade Federal do ABC (UFABC)

Abstract:

INTRODUÇÃO: As vias de termorregulação relacionadas ao frio avançaram após a descoberta dos canais TRP sensíveis à temperatura (do inglês, Transient Receptor Potential). A estimulação aguda dos canais TRPM8 periférico mimetiza a exposição ao frio e altera a atividade do núcleo parabraquial lateral (LPB) e área pré-óptica do hipotálamo (POA), resultando na ativação de termofetores de defesa ao frio, como termogênese e vasoconstrição cutânea. Este estudo tem como objetivo avaliar a expressão de c-Fos, um marcador de atividade neuronal no LPB e POA em resposta ao tratamento crônico com mentol. **METODOLOGIA:** Foram tratados ratos Wistar machos adultos com mentol (5%) ou veículo (propilenoglicol) topicamente (pele do dorso do animal) por 1, 3 ou 9 dias consecutivos. A temperatura corporal e o peso corporal foram medidos diariamente. Duas horas após o tratamento, os ratos foram eutanasiados e os cérebros removidos foram fixados em PFA e crioprotetidos. Posteriormente, os cérebros foram seccionados (35 µm) e foi realizada imuno-histoquímica para c-Fos nas regiões de interesse. As lâminas foram fotografadas e a contagem de células imunorreativas para c-Fos foi realizada de forma cega por um único examinador usando o software ImageJ (NIH). **RESULTADOS E CONCLUSÃO:** A estimulação crônica com mentol (tratamento tópico) em ratos Wistar alimentados com dieta normal (não calórica) elevou a temperatura corporal dos animais devido ao maior gasto energético para manter a homeostase interna sem alterar o consumo alimentar, levando a um menor ganho de massa corporal em mentol ratos tratados. Nós avaliamos a expressão de c-Fos na principal região do cérebro envolvida em resposta à exposição ao frio, uma vez que o mentol exógeno mimetiza a exposição ao frio. Verificamos que o mentol aumenta o número de células positivas para c-fos na POA (aumento de 30%), após o primeiro tratamento, e esse aumento na ativação de POA persiste (3 ou 9 dias, 27 e

aumento de 49%) após o tratamento crônico com mentol. **NOVIDADE:** POA, uma região importante envolvida na resposta ao frio, também é ativada após estimulação aguda e crônica dos canais TRPM8 com mentol.

Palavras Chave: termorregulação, hipertermia, TRPM8

Presentation:

Title:

A HISTÓRIA DAS CÉLULAS HELA: UMA DISCUSSÃO SOBRE BIOÉTICA..

Glória Helena Ribeiro Alfa Santucci – Universidade Federal do ABC.

Abstract:

Introdução: O século XX foi marcado pelo avanço da biotecnologia, muitas vezes, contudo, em detrimento de questões éticas e de direitos humanos, como o caso de Henrietta Lacks (1920-51), talvez um dos maiores anonimatos da ciência. Em 1951, no Hospital Universitário John Hopkins(EUA), ela foi diagnosticada com uma forma atípica de câncer. Células retiradas do tumor, sem seu consentimento ou conhecimento, não só sobreviveram como se multiplicaram indefinidamente em laboratório, fenômeno este biologicamente único. Por essa razão, sua linhagem, chamada de “HeLa”, foi utilizada para entender o metabolismo celular, desenvolver vacinas (como a da Poliomielite) e foi até levada ao espaço. Lacks, porém, morreu no mesmo ano da coleta, e sua família demorou mais de vinte para descobrir que as células HeLa estavam espalhadas aos milhões pelo mundo. Recentemente descendentes iniciaram um movimento que envolve comunidade científica e sociedade pelo justo reconhecimento e reparação por tais contribuições. Esse trabalho visa colaborar com esse esforço. Objetivos: discutir sob o ponto de vista Bioético o caso de Henrietta Lacks, sua singularidade e como foram tratadas a ética e moral dos envolvidos. Metodologia: Informações foram extraídas da literatura médica e de relatos biográficos. Os conceitos discutidos passam por Kant e Beauchamp, sendo orientados pela bioética, princípios e virtudes. O método empregado foi de revisão bibliográfica e discussão teórica, com achados recentes e estudos diversos. Resultados: A análise demonstra como os princípios fundamentais da bioética - Autonomia, Equidade, Justiça, Beneficência, Não-Maleficência- foram distorcidos no sequestro da linhagem HeLa e nos processos exploratórios dele resultante. Conclusão: os achados reafirmam a necessidade, atualmente defendida por outras discussões emergentes entre Academia, Governos e Sociedade, de seguir desconstruindo métodos e epistemologias da ciência moderna buscando que contribuições para o desenvolvimento da humanidade não sejam mais invisibilizadas, como ocorre historicamente nos demais campos do conhecimento.

Presentation:

Title:

O PAPEL NEUROPROTETOR DE PEPTÍDEOS ANTIOXIDANTES EM DIFERENTES MODELOS CELULARES DA ESCLEROSE LATERAL AMIOTRÓFICA.

Guilherme Garuti dos Santos¹, Jorge Torresi¹, Ariel Sztterling¹, Luciana Malavolta Quaglio¹, Rosenstock TR¹ - ¹Departament of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP.

Abstract:

A Esclerose Lateral Amiotrófica (ELA) é uma doença neurodegenerativa rara caracterizada pela degeneração progressiva de neurônios motores seguida de atrofia muscular. Pelo fato do aumento dos níveis de estresse oxidativo estar relacionado com o desenvolvimento dessa neuropatologia degenerativa, o objetivo desse projeto é verificar a ação neuroprotetora de diferentes peptídeos antioxidantes frente a disfunção mitocondrial, que é a principal causa do aumento de espécies reativas de oxigênio, nomeadamente quanto a modificações no metabolismo e na dinâmica dessa organela. Para isso, foram utilizados diferentes modelos da ELA: neurônios expostos a peróxido de hidrogênio (H₂O₂) e tert-Butil hidroperóxido (t-Butil). As células SH-SY5Y (neuroblastomas humanos) foram cultivadas em meio DMEM-F12 suplementado e tratadas com diferentes concentrações de H₂O₂ (2 mM, por 1 hora) e t-Butil (2mM, por 1 hora) para averiguar a sobrevivência celular. Além disso, dois diferentes peptídeos antioxidantes foram utilizados para o mesmo fim, o DN1605 (Thr-Arg-Asn-Tyr-Tyr-Val-Arg-Val-Leu-OH) e a carnosina (H-β-Ala-His-OH). Para mensurar a viabilidade celular, foram realizados experimentos com o Vybrant® MTT Cell Proliferation Assay Kit. Já para analisar o metabolismo mitocondrial, as células foram plaqueadas em MW96 e o potencial de membrana mitocondrial foi avaliado usando o indicador fluorimétrico TMRE (500nM, 1 hora a 37°C), o cálcio intracelular foi averiguado utilizando o fluoróforo Fluo-3-AM (10 μM, 1 hora, 37°C) e os níveis de estresse oxidativo com o indicador H2DCFDA (20 μM, 1 hora, 37°C). Podemos observar que há um aumento da morte celular frente aos indutores de estresse oxidativo, e que essa morte é inibida frente os antioxidantes testados. Verificamos também que as condições para avaliação do metabolismo mitocondrial nesse sistema está estável e padronizado, e o próximo passo será a medição da diferença de sinal entre os grupos, e posteriormente ao tratamento com os antioxidantes.

Presentation:

Title:

ACTION OF LYSINE (K)-DEACETYLASE MODULATORS ON CELL METABOLISM IN ASTROCYTES EXPOSED TO OXIDATIVE STRESS AND EXCITOTOXICITY.

Torresi JLB¹, Dutra MB¹, Rosenstock TRR¹ - ¹Departament of Physiological Sciences – FCMSCSP.

Abstract:

Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal neurodegenerative disease, in which approximately 90% of the cases are sporadic. Although mitochondrial dysfunction, augmentation in the oxidative stress levels and excitotoxicity being the main neuropathological features of ALS, the disease is multifactorial and, therefore, several mechanisms are been investigated to establish a neuroprotective strategy against it. Considering this, epigenetic modifications, such as histones acetylation, are in the spotlight and the lysines (K)-deacetylases (KDACs) are the main enzymes enrolled in this process. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate mitochondrial function in different ALS pharmacological models as well as the possible neuroprotective role of KDAC inhibitors. The models used in this work was astrocytes exposed to H₂O₂ (oxidative stress model) and to the neurotoxina L-BMAA (excitotoxicity model); it was used HDAC inhibitors named TSA, SB, MS-275 and SBHA. We found the restoration of cell survival via the treatment with said drugs, except SBHA, the treatment having restored viability back to control levels. KDACs inhibitors seem to be beneficial and neuroprotective in the oxidative stress model, improving cellular survival due to changes, to normal values, in the mitochondrial membrane potential.

Presentation:**Title:**

MITOCHONDRIAL DYSFUNCTION AND HYPOXIA AS A PATHOLOGICAL HALLMARKS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCHIZOPHRENIA

Luiz Felipe Souza e Silva^{1*}, Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock^{1*} - ¹Faculdade de Ciências Médicas da Santa Casa de São Paulo, São Paulo, Brasil; *souza.luiz11@gmail.com

Abstract:

Schizophrenia is a multifactorial mental disorder and one of the related factors is mitochondrial dysfunction. Taking into account that environmental factors seem to interact with the development of brain tissue and that, astrocytes support neurons energetically and play an essential role in this period, mitochondrial function is of the utmost importance and, therefore, intra-uterine hypoxia could cause mitochondrial changes and, consequently, cause abnormalities in astrocyte energy metabolism and neurodevelopmental impairments. The objective of this study was to verify mitochondrial function in astrocytes in a model associated with schizophrenic disorder who suffers from an intra-uterine hypoxia situation (spontaneously hypertensive rats - SHR). For this, several fluorescent methods were used to analyse the mitochondrial metabolism, Fluo-4-AM (10 μ M) for cytosolic calcium homeostasis (cCa^{2+}). TMRE (500 nM) for mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$) and levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), H₂DCF-DA (20 μ M) for general ROS and MitoSox (5 μ M) for superoxide (O_2^-). In addition, real-time PCR and Western blot technique was used to analyse the expression of genes and levels of proteins related to mitochondria dynamics. The data revealed that mitochondria submitted to neonatal hypoxia (SHR) accumulate more Ca^{2+} since they have lower basal cytosolic fluorescence (W: 100% \pm 5 x SHR: 84% \pm 1) and they are depolarized in relation to the CTR group (W: 100% \pm 4 x SHR: 123% \pm 4). In addition, there is an elevation of general ROS (W: 100% \pm 4 x SHR: 190% \pm 6) and O_2^- (W: 100% \pm 1 x SHR: 131,4% \pm 6) in SHR astrocytes. Furthermore, there is an increase in the mitochondrial fission process (increased *Drp-1* gene expression: W: 100% \pm 0,1 x SHR:125% \pm 0,06) and a decrease in genes related to fusion mechanism (*Mfn-2* gene expression: W:100% \pm 0 x SHR:60% \pm 0,09) in SHR group. However, we observe increase of mitochondrial biogenesis genes like, *Pgc1a* (W: 100% \pm 0,14 x SHR: 185% \pm 0,23), with an increase in levels of the TOM-40 protein (W: 100% \pm 6 x SHR: 157% \pm 1,6) which reinforces the hypothesis of the largest number of mitochondria in the astrocytes of SHR rats. In addition, we also observed an increase in *Tfam* (100% \pm 0,3 x SHR: 120% \pm 0,05) and mtDNA (*Tco1*) (W:100% \pm 0,01 x SHR:148% \pm 0,07) genes expression, both related to the process of mitochondrial biogenesis. As a conclusion, neonatal hypoxia is capable of modifying mitochondrial metabolism and dynamics causing abnormalities in its functioning. The decline in mitochondrial function of astrocytes, driven by the hypoxia pathway, therefore, can lead to an impaired neurodevelopment and increase vulnerability to the onset of schizophrenic disorder.

Presentation:

Title:

MITOCHONDRIAL METABOLISM IN AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS PHARMACOLOGICAL MODELS.

Mariana Dutra Brito¹ Tatiana Rosado Rosenstock¹ - ¹Santa Casa de São Paulo School of Medical Sciences, São Paulo, SP.

Abstract:

Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal neurodegenerative disease, in which approximately 90% of the cases are sporadic. Mitochondrial dysfunction, augmentation in oxidative stress levels and excitotoxicity being the main neuropathological features in ALS considered a multifactorial disorder. The objective of this study is to evaluate the mitochondrial metabolism in different cellular models of ALS: astrocytes after 1) induction of oxidative stress (with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)), and 2) glutamatergic imbalance (with the neurotoxin L-BMAA) Mitochondrial function was assessed by spectrofluorimetry using different fluorescence indicators: mitochondrial membrane potential was evaluated with TMRE (500nM), cytosolic Ca²⁺ with Fluo-4 AM (10µM) and oxidative stress with H₂DCFDA (20µM). We also evaluated the gene expression of the transcriptional co-factor PGC-1alpha, related to mitochondrial biogenesis. In basal conditions, the mitochondria of L-BMAA and H₂O₂ treated cells are depolarized in relation to the control group. In addition, we observed a depolarization of the mitochondria after treatments with L-BMAA and H₂O₂ in the presence of FCCP. Regarding to L-BMAA treated cells, they also showed a significant decrease in PGC-1alpha expression. We conclude that the drugs used here as pharmacological models of ALS alter mitochondrial function through the induction of mitochondrial membrane depolarization; this, in turn, can be related to changes in mitochondrial biogenesis and an increase in a cell death.

Presentation:

Title:

ESTUDO DA MODULAÇÃO DOS COMPOSTOS CANNABINOIDES NA AUTOFAGIA MEDIADA PELO TFEB EM MODELO CELULAR DE TAUPATIA

Talita Aparecida de Moraes Vrechi¹, Rodrigo Portes Ureshin¹, Vanessa Costhek Abílio¹, Diego Medina², Sandip Patel³, Gian Maria Fimia⁴, Gustavo José da Silva Pereira¹ - ¹Departamento de Farmacologia, EPM-UNIFESP; ² Telethon Institute of Genetics and Medicine, Naples, Italy; ³ University College London, London, UK; ⁴ Istituto Nazionale per le Malattie Infettive "L.Spallanzani", Rome, Italy

Abstract:

A doença de Alzheimer (DA) é uma das doenças neurodegenerativas mais estudadas na atualidade sendo uma das principais causas de demência em idosos. A presença da proteína Tau hiperfosforilada nos neurônios é um dos principais marcadores histológicos da DA, porém a sua presença também pode ser encontrada em outras doenças chamadas taupatias, no qual podem causar morte neuronal. Sabe-se que disfunções autofágicas podem ocorrer na neurodegeneração, levando a formação e acúmulo de agregados proteicos tóxicos. Dessa forma, a modulação da autofagia tem sido postulada como um possível alvo terapêutico, na qual a ativação do fator de transcrição EB (TFEB) é uma importante e recente via de indução desse processo. Estudos ainda sugerem que os compostos canabinoides apresentam um papel neuroprotetor em modelos de neurodegeneração, porém a via de regulação autofágica mediada por esses compostos é desconhecida. A partir desses pressupostos, o objetivo geral deste projeto será investigar a inter-relação dos agonistas do sistema canabinoide com a via autofágica mediada pelo TFEB e seus possíveis mecanismos neuroprotetores em um modelo neuronal *in vitro* de taupatia. Para tanto, a linhagem neuronal SH-SY5Y, superexpressando a proteína Tau humana, será tratada com compostos canabinoides e por meio de técnicas de microscopia de fluorescência e de biologia molecular, como *Western Blotting* e PCR em tempo real, serão realizados estudos de proteínas e genes regulatórios da via autofágica e de morte celular modulada pelo sistema canabinoide. Dessa forma, acreditamos poder contribuir para um melhor entendimento sobre o papel dos canabinoides na indução autofágica, e assim colaborar para um potencial desenvolvimento de novas terapias em taupatias.

Palavras-chave: Doença de Alzheimer, Taupatias, Autofagia, Canabinoides, TFEB.